

CRACKING AND DELAMINATION OF CROSS- AND ANGLE PLY GFRP BENDING SPECIMENS UNDER VERY HIGH CYCLE FATIGUE LOADING

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ABSTRACT

High frequency bending fatigue experiments are conducted to investigate damage mechanisms and stiffness degradation of GFRP flat specimens in very high cycle ranges. By using a special VHCF test rig and testing at frequencies between 50 Hz and 80 Hz the so called very high cycle fatigue range is reached within a reasonable amount of time. Online stiffness measurement, transmitted light photography and thermography are used for damage monitoring. Comprehensive fatigue data of $[90/0]_s$ cross-ply laminates tested up to 10^8 cycles have already been published. Here, first results of an angle-ply layup $[\pm 45]_s$ are presented. The evolution of crack densities and delaminated area fractions are investigated for several load levels. At low load amplitudes, a fatigue limit becomes apparent.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fatigue of fibre-reinforced plastics (FRP) is a complex issue and has been one of the main focuses in composite research since the 1960s. A broad base of knowledge concerning the mechanisms of fatigue, their interaction as well as numerous theoretical modeling approaches has been established. Even though there are numerous applications reaching the so-called very high cycle fatigue (VHCF) range (e.g. GFRP wind turbine rotor blades due to service times of up to 30 years or light-weight CFRP compressor blades of aero engines due to frequency), experimental experience is mostly limited to the high cycle fatigue range (HCF, 1×10^6 cycles) rarely exceeding 1×10^7 cycles. In fact, the very high cycle fatigue behavior of FRP has not been sufficiently investigated yet [1]. The lack of knowledge beyond HCF is usually compensated by conservative designs.

1.1. Available studies on VHCF of composite materials

A series of early studies regarding the long-term fatigue of wind turbine rotor blades has been conducted at the Montana State University in the 1990s. Mandell *et al.* [2-4] tested several wind turbine blade materials under the auspices of the U.S. DOE's Wind Energy Program. Most tests were constant-amplitude SN tests using standard coupon tests as well as a high speed test procedure allowing tests with frequencies up to 100 Hz. Cycle numbers of up to 10^{10} are reached by means of testing thin fibre strand specimens at frequencies of 200 Hz. However, the authors state that nominal defect free fibre strands cannot be compared to laminate specimens due to the size effect. More recent very-high-cycle fatigue tests were conducted by Hosoi *et al.* [5-9]. Generally, experiments with lowered stress amplitudes lead to extended fatigue lives. Hosoi *et al.* show that tensile load amplitudes of about 30 % of the static failure stress shift failure into the VHCF range. The effect of stress level on the growth rates of transversal matrix cracks and delamination is investigated with quasi-isotropic CFRP tensile specimens. While stress levels of 60 % of the static fracture load lead to matrix cracks before delamination is initiated, lower stress amplitudes cause delamination to occur earlier to or simultaneously with the transversal cracking. Furthermore, it is stated that stress levels of 20 % do

neither lead to matrix cracking nor to delamination up to cycle numbers of 2.0×10^8 . Another recent approach to VHCF, using a shaker-based bending test rig, is presented by Gude *et al.* [10]. Backe *et al.* [11] attempt to test interlaminar shear GFRP specimens at ultrasonic frequencies. Tests have to be pulsed to manage specimen heating.

Comprehensive fatigue data of $[90/0]_s$ cross-ply laminates tested up to 10^8 cycles has been published by the authors in [15]. Transverse cracking and delamination are found to be the major damage mechanisms when load levels are close to the fiber-transverse strength. In all cases, transverse cracks mainly initiate at free edges and then grow in two directions – across the width and in thickness direction. Thereby, the crack growth rate in thickness direction is found to be crucial for the initiation of delamination. Along with fatigue, bending stiffness decreases, correlating well with increasing crack densities and delaminated area fractions. It is found that delamination does not occur at all below a certain fiber-transverse stress level. Testing at even lower loads reveals the existence of a threshold for the onset of transverse cracking. Below this threshold, the occurrence of scattered cracks not forming a regular crack pattern is interpreted as weak area cracking.

1.2 Challenges of VHCF testing

When testing in the very-high-cycle fatigue range, numerous difficulties and requirements concerning the testing equipment, the test specimens as well as the damage monitoring have to be solved. One main inconvenience results from the fibre-reinforced composite material itself. In contrast to metals, which can easily be tested at kHz frequencies, polymer materials have higher material dampings. In combination with low thermal conductivities, high-frequency testing usually ends in excessive hysteretic specimen heating. Usually, this problem is overcome by limiting specimen thickness (Mandell *et al.*: $t = 1.5$ mm and fibre strands, Hosoi *et al.*: $t = 1.1$ mm). In addition to overheating, further difficulties concern the measuring of stress parameters. Mandell *et al.* report failures of bonded strain gages and slipping of fatigue extensometers. Another aspect of testing is material strength. Some glass fibre-reinforced plastics reach ultimate tensile strengths of about 1000 MPa. Thus, when driving standard testing machines (Mandell: MTS 880, Hosoi: not specified hydraulic-driven machine) into the very high-cycle fatigue range, self-fatigue of the testing equipment might be a side effect.

2 EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

In this study, a specialized test rig developed in [13-15] is used. Its main asset is that testing times are shortened by testing at frequencies between 50 to 80 Hz. The heating problem is circumvented by using a four-point bending load case. Additional air cooling helps to keep temperature increase below 15 °C. Several online damage monitoring techniques are directly integrated into the test rig which allows to investigate degradation behavior, damage mechanisms and phenomenology at VHCF loads without interrupting the tests.

2.1. VHCF Bending Test Rig and Damage Monitoring

A test rig for high frequent VHCF four-point bending has been set up. Due to the four-point-bending, a large area of uniform damage growth can be investigated. An overview of the test rig with four bending platforms is depicted in Figure 1. Each platform is an independent bending test as depicted in Fig. 1 (B). It is driven by a customized electrodynamic actuator providing frequencies of up to 80 Hz (non-resonant), depending on the specimen configuration. A flat bending specimen ($t = 2$ mm, $w = 25$ mm, $l = 82$ mm) is embedded in a two-sided light-weight four-point bending device ($R = -I$). Eight rotatable low-friction rollers (four on each side of the specimen) prevent frictional heating and abrasive damage of the specimen. With the middle part of the device deflected by a light-weight actuator rod, a sinusoidal bending load is applied. Both parameters load (one load f on each side of the device) and maximum deflection d_a are measured online by means of two load cells and a triangulation laser. The measurement of load and deflection is used for two purposes. Firstly, for controlling load or deflection by means of a control circuit in *Lab View*®. Secondly, for calculating the dynamic secant bending modulus in terms of damage monitoring. Furthermore, two optical techniques, thermography and transmitted light photography, have been integrated into the test rig.

Especially transmitted light photography, which is based on a flat cold light lamp in the moving part of the bending device, provides detailed images of matrix cracking and delamination in transparent or opaque GFRP materials. All monitoring techniques are online techniques to prevent undesired effects due to removing the specimen for characterization throughout the test. Another aspect is the control of ambient temperature. As bending forces are relatively small ($30 \text{ N} \leq f_a \leq 500 \text{ N}$) and most light-weight devices are made of aluminum, changes in ambient temperature have undesired effects. Therefore, the rig is housed in an air-conditioned chamber with a temperature of $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \pm 1.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 1: Overview of the VHCF test rig with four bending units (A), concept of the bending device (B)

2.2. Damage Evaluation

Fatigue damage is evaluated in two different ways, by continuously calculating the loss in bending stiffness throughout the test and by determination of crack densities and delaminated areas. The specimens' effective bending (secant) modulus \bar{E}_{xb} is calculated by means of the 4-point bending equation and the geometric parameters. With the specimen thickness t , its width w , the distance between the middle pair of rollers b (40 mm) and the length of the outer specimen regions a (20 mm) the bending modulus is

$$\bar{E}_{xb} = \frac{f_a}{d_a} \frac{6}{wt^3} \left(\frac{1}{3} a^3 + \frac{1}{2} b a^2 + \frac{1}{8} a b^2 \right) \quad (1)$$

The bar implies a simplification concerning the calculation of the elastic modulus of the damaged specimen. In case of an undamaged specimen, \bar{E}_{xb} can be determined from the maximum bending deflection and force. In contrast, with the fatigue damage decreasing towards both ends of the specimen, this approach does not reflect the stiffness loss of the uniformly damaged central region accurately. However, the influence of the undamaged specimen regions has been found to be small and \bar{E}_{xb} only deviates slightly from E_{xb} [16].

Concerning the optical monitoring, an average transverse crack density of the constantly stressed middle part of the specimen is calculated by the sum of all crack lengths per window area. As cracks grow equally in both sides of the specimen ($R = -1$) and as this cannot be differentiated in the transmitted light pictures, crack length is divided by two.

$$\rho_{90^\circ} = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^n l_{crack,i}}{2 \cdot l_{window} \cdot w_{specimen}} \quad (2)$$

Furthermore, the total debonded area A_{delam} , which is measured by means of digital image analysis, is used to calculate the delaminated area fraction.

$$daf_{90^\circ} = \frac{A_{delam}}{2 \cdot l_{window} \cdot w_{specimen}} \quad (3)$$

2.3 Material and Specimen Preparation

All specimens tested are $[\pm 45]_s$ GFRP flat specimen with a laminate thickness of 2 mm and four single-layers of 0.5 mm. As sewing threads are imperfections causing inner heating (at higher frequencies) and given that they affect the crack and delamination observation as well, the laminate is produced unsewn by CNC roving stacking and RTM. The constituents are glass fibre rovings Owens Corning OC111AX (1200 tex) and a cold curing epoxy system Momentive RIM135/RIMH137. The average fibre volume fraction is 0.42. After cutting to specimen size, edges are polished to remove micro cracks.

2.4 Specimen Parameters and Load Levels

Load controlled cyclic tests are conducted at several load levels (LL1 to LL4) to investigate the effect of cyclic load amplitude. The strategy is to begin with high load amplitudes causing fatigue failure in the high cycle fatigue range (HCF). Then, load is lowered stepwise to shift final failure to high cycle numbers. In contrast to the cross-ply laminate tested before, stress state characterization is more complex in case of a $[\pm 45]_s$ configuration. As momentum fluxes (m_x, m_y, m_{xy}) and curvatures ($\kappa_x, \kappa_y, \kappa_{xy}$) are fully coupled, m_x causes a curvature κ_x as well as anticlastic deformation κ_y and twisting κ_{xy} . In case of a so-called *slim beam*, all curvatures may occur without constraints, leading to the analytically calculated ply stresses depicted in Figure 2 (A). However, as specimen geometry is rather wide (width to height ratio 12.5), *wide beam* assumptions are applicable and (B) depicts the effect of κ_y being suppressed. Indeed, more or less unratable constraints may result from the four-point bending device and its rollers. Pictures (C) and (D) point out noticeable changes in stress state by additionally suppressing anticlastic deformation κ_y or both κ_y and κ_{xy} .

Figure 2: Analytically calculated stress state of a $[\pm 45]_s$ laminate depending on the curvature boundary conditions, $\kappa_x = \text{const}$.

To clarify the influences of the bending device, a more sophisticated numerical model is used. Figure 3 depicts a four-point bending specimen modelled with hexahedron elements and contact boundary conditions in *MSC Patran*®. For simplification, all four rollers are frictionless. Each ply contains 8 elements in thickness direction and 56 elements across the width. Nonlinear analysis is conducted with *Abaqus*®. The example contour plot depicts a typical deformation state. In post processing, longitudinal and transverse deformations are extracted nodewise along the designated paths. Then, global curvatures are determined by means of least square circle fitting. Besides κ_x ($\kappa_x = -0.00456$ at $y = 0$) anticlastic bending κ_y occurs ($\kappa_y = 0.00258$ at $x = 0$). As expected, anticlastic deformation changes towards the rollers ($\kappa_y = 0.00186$ at $y = \pm 20$). Furthermore, the deflection curves extracted at $y = +20$ and $y = -20$ indicate a slight twisting. To clarify the effect of the rollers on the stress state, ply stresses are extracted at three locations along the x-axis (Figure 4 A). Fibre-parallel and transverse stresses are found to slightly increase towards the rollers, whereas in-plane shear stress decreases. However, changes are moderate. Comparison with the four cases discussed above (Figure 2) makes clear that scenario (D) assuming anticlastic bending but suppressed twisting is close to the numerical results. In fact, fitting the analytical model to the numerical data reveals that twisting curvature is constrained to approximately 3 % of κ_{xy} in the *slim beam* case while κ_y is less affected (94 % of $\kappa_{y,slim}$).

Figure 3: Deformation of a $[\pm 45]_s$ four-point bending specimen modelled with hexahedron elements and contact boundary conditions, effect of rollers on anticlastic curvature

Another aspect is the formation of interlaminar stresses towards the free edge. In contrast to the undisturbed stress state, noticeable interlaminar shear stresses occur close to the edge. Although stress peaks are limited to a narrow region, these areas are prone to initiation and progression of free-edge delamination.

Figure 4: Stress state at different locations, effect of longitudinal position (A) on ply stresses, interlaminar stresses due to free-edge effect (B)

By means of the numerical model, several load levels for fatigue testing have been defined. All values summarized in Table 1 are maximum surface amplitude stresses under single-sided bending.

Load Level	$\epsilon_{x,0}$ (%)	σ_{11}^{+45} (MPa)	σ_{22}^{+45} (MPa)	τ_{12}^{+45} (MPa)
LL1	0.46	39.4	12.9	-20.0
LL2	0.38	32.2	10.7	-16.3
LL3	0.32	27.2	9.0	-13.8
LL4	0.27	22.8	7.5	-11.5

Table 1: Load level averages, stresses and strains are single-sided bending surface values in the undisturbed middle part of the specimen ($x = 0, y = 0$ in Fig. 3)

2.5 Load level Accuracy and Frequency Effects

Besides the challenges discussed in section 1.2, a further issue has to be dealt with when testing at low load levels. Typically, data scattering (e.g. in terms of fatigue cycles) is worse in high cycle fatigue. This is due to several reasons taking effect at lower load amplitudes. Material defects, for example, usually playing a subordinate role at higher loads may predominantly cause damage initiation at lower loads. Another aspect is the accuracy of the applied load. In VHCF a slight deviation from the intended load may cause a multiple ten million cycles variation in fatigue life. Due to this reason, several tests were conducted trying to assess the test rig's accuracy concerning the load amplitude and resulting specimen strain. Figure 5 (A) compares the longitudinal surface strain amplitude of a bending specimen determined by means of the maximum bending deflection, a strain gauge measurement and a 2D laser scanner (B). All three values are in good agreement. Whereas the difference between calculation and strain gauge measurement is below 1 % the laser scanner value deviates more than 2.5 %. This is presumably due to the limited measuring frequency of the scanner (200 Hz). All in all, the resulting longitudinal strain seems to be rather accurate.

Figure 5: Accuracy of resulting longitudinal surface stress, comparison of calculation and experimentally determined values (strain gauge and laser scanning measurement)

Another important issue is the role of testing frequency affecting damage propagation and fatigue life. Concerning this matter, contradictory conclusions may be found in literature. However, experiments without specimen cooling and temperature control might not allow significant conclusions. In contrast, Apinis[12], Mandell *et al.* and Hosoi *et al.* prove that high frequencies or strain rates do not affect fatigue life, as long as temperatures are controlled and kept far below the glass transition temperature. With respect to the recent project, the authors will address that topic in upcoming test series. So far, strain rate effects have been considered regarding the load control. As bending deflection and strain rate increase throughout the tests, changes in dynamic stiffness would affect the load control. Thus, the strain rate dependence of the bending modulus has been investigated for three different laminate types $[\pm 45]_s$, $[90/0]_s$ and a less matrix dependent regular cross-ply $[0/90]_s$. Strain rate has been varied in two ways, by increasing frequency while bending deflection is held constant (Figure 6 A) and by increasing bending deflection with the specimens tested at fixed frequencies (B). The latter case equals the load-controlled tests. Apart from data scattering, strain rate does not affect bending modulus conspicuously. Especially diagram (B) representing the more relevant case does not reveal any undesired changes in dynamic stiffness. However, all dynamic moduli are slightly higher than the static ones which is a typical effect present at low strain rates (e.g. strain-rate effects in quasi-static tests). Above, bending modulus is constant within the considered range. Unfortunately, resonant behavior of the load-cells causes inaccurate force measurement and irregular high bending moduli at frequencies around 70 Hz (A).

Figure 6: Dependency of dynamic stiffness and strain rate, strain rate change due to frequency (A, const. deflection) and bending deflection (B, const. frequency),

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

So far, 27 specimens of an unsewn [± 45]_s GFRP laminate have been tested at four different load levels listed in Table 1. Each test starts at an initial deflection and a resulting initial longitudinal surface strain $\varepsilon_{x,0}$. Corresponding ply-stresses were calculated by means of a numerical model. The strategy was to lower the load amplitude from one load level to the next to investigate changes in fatigue behaviour – from HCF to VHCF.

All specimens tested at the higher load levels (LL1, LL2) show the typical degradation behavior known from axial tests. Figure 7 depicts the typical three stages from initiation to final failure. Right in the beginning, matrix cracking originates from the free edges of the outer 45°-ply and grows in two directions – across the width and in thickness direction. Bending stiffness decreases rapidly due to the outer ply cracking and forms an elbow in stiffness decrease. Inner ply cracking and edge delamination initiates. Afterwards, stiffness degradation progresses rather linearly with cycle number due to steady crack- and delamination growth. At this stage, the outer ply cracking has saturated. In the end, with the delaminated area becoming critical, bending stiffness drops due to outer ply separation.

Figure 7: Modulus degradation due to fatigue damage, exemplary data depicting a typical three-staged fatigue life, transmitted light images showing matrix cracking and delamination

Regarding the interaction of cracking and delamination, both mechanisms develop in the well-known manner. With the outer crack reaching the ply interface, two mechanisms - local delamination and inner ply cracking are activated. Scattered initiation of internal cracks is found as well. Due to the alternating bending ($R = -1$), damage grows equally on both sides of the laminate.

Figure 8: Exemplary crack pass development in outer and inner plies (A), internally initiated cracks, incident light (B) and silight (C)

Damage initiation and propagation clearly depends on the load amplitude. Whereas stiffness decrease and final failure occurs between 4×10^6 and 7×10^6 cycles in the case of LL1, laminate rupture is shifted beyond 1×10^7 at LL2. The majority of all specimens tested at LL2 fails at about 2×10^7 cycles. In all cases, final failure occurs when bending stiffness decreases below 65 – 70 % of the initial stiffness value. At lower load levels (LL3 and LL4), stiffness decreases slower and final failure does not occur except for one specimen. Instead, degradation levels off in the range between 70 – 80 % at LL3. In fact, there is no further loss in bending stiffness between 2×10^7 and 1.5×10^8 cycles. With respect to time consumption test were stopped at 1×10^8 or 1.5×10^8 cycles, respectively. At LL4, stiffness decreases even slower without levelling off distinctly in the range up to 1×10^8 cycles.

Figure 8: Effect of load level on modulus degradation

Crack densities and delaminated area fractions are calculated to characterize the underlying damage mechanisms evolution. Regarding the outer ply crack growth, damage progression correlates well with the stiffness degradation curves. Outer ply cracking is the predominating damage mechanism with respect to stiffness degradation. In case of LL1, outer ply crack densities ρ_{+45} reach values about 0.6 1/mm just before final failure. At LL2 and LL3, outer ply crack density attains similar values in the range between about 0.5 1/mm to 0.6 1/mm. However, there are distinct differences in inner ply cracking and delamination behavior. Generally, inner ply cracking is delayed at all load levels.

Figure 9: Effect of load level on crack density evolution in outer (-) and inner plies (--)

Whereas the inner plies reach similar crack densities ρ_{-45} like the outer plies in case of LL1 and LL2, ρ_{-45} stays lower at LL3 only reaching half the values on average. The lower extent of outer ply cracking impedes the progression of delamination and inner ply cracking. In contrast to the higher load levels, damage state does not become critical in the cycle range tested. At LL4, even the outer ply crack densities stay low with hardly any inner ply cracking resulting in minor stiffness degradation. Regarding delamination growth, load level differences are even more distinctive. In contrast to LL1 and LL2 showing extensive delamination growth and delaminated area fractions around 35 % at final failure, LL3 area fractions stay below 20 % in most cases.

Figure 11: Effect of load level on delamination growth

On the whole, delamination growth slows down extremely at cycle numbers beyond 2×10^7 . At LL4, delamination growth is negligible and limited to a narrow band around outer ply cracks not reaching area fractions greater than 3%.

Cycles to failure are extracted from the so far discussed results and plotted against the corresponding initial longitudinal surface strain $\epsilon_{x,0}$ in Figure 12. In addition, recent high cycle fatigue results ($N < 10^6$) of a higher load level LL0 have been included. With log-scaled cycles, a typical strain-life relationship is revealed and represented by a logarithmic regression curve. As most specimens tested at load levels LL2 to LL4 do not reach final failure, they are declared as run out specimens and plotted at the cycle number of test interruption. The number above indicates the particular number of specimens stopped at the same time. Despite the data scattering, a fatigue limit with respect to final rupture becomes apparent. However, as run out specimens are damaged to a certain degree and as delamination and inner ply cracking has not come to rest in the cycle range up to 1.5×10^8 , a delay of rupture has to be considered. The identification of a damage initiation threshold (cf. [15] for $[90/0]_s$ lay-up) might be an interesting issue as well. In case of LL4 e.g. load amplitude is too small to initiate inner ply cracking. All in all, additional specimens have to be tested at intermediate (between LL2 and LL3) and even lower load levels.

Figure 12: Preliminary $\epsilon_0 N$ diagram, plotting the initial longitudinal strain against the number of cycles to failure

4 CONCLUSIONS

A series of $[\pm 45]_s$ GFRP cross-ply specimen has been tested up to load cycles beyond 1×10^8 by means of a specialized high frequency four-point bending fatigue test rig. Stiffness degradation, transverse cracking and delamination are monitored with online techniques. Then, damage parameters (crack densities and delaminated area fractions) are calculated to investigate the effect of load level and the fatigue process at low loads. Outer ply cracking is the dominant, stiffness degrading mechanisms and present at all loads tested. Delamination growth strongly depends on load amplitude. At low loads, delamination propagates much slower delaying final failure. At even lower loads, delaminated area does not reach critical values and inner ply cracking does not occur. Regarding fatigue life, reducing load amplitude by a third shifts final failure from HCF ($< 10^6$, LL0) to very high cycle numbers $> 10^7$ (LL2). Half the load of does not result in final failure in the range up to 10^8 cycles. Besides the load dependent changes in cracking- and delamination behavior, no unexpected mechanisms have been found. Further tests will be conducted at intermediate and even lower load levels.

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